

The Marie Skłodowska Curie Project Initial Training Network (ITN) on Digital Cultural Heritage (DCH) Final Conference on Digital Heritage

23rd-25th May 2017

Olimje, Slovenia

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Aleš Gruden
Olimje (Slovenia)

ITN-DCH FINAL CONFERENCE

Hotel Sotelia, Olimje, Slovenia

23rd-25nd May 2017

ITN-DCH FINAL CONFERENCE is an international event for the professionals of multiple disciplines and scholars working in the Digital Cultural Heritage domain. The aim of the conference is to bring together experts, stakeholders and researchers from the cultural domain and, addressing the current challenges, start a dialogue that will lay the foundation for the creation of a multidisciplinary community of practice..

The “Initial Training Network for Digital Cultural Heritage: Projecting our Past to the Future” (<http://itn-dch.eu/>) with acronym ITN-DCH, is the first and one of the largest Marie Curie fellowship projects in the area of the e-documentation / e-preservation and CH protection funded by the European Union under the FP7 PEOPLE research framework. The Project started on the 1st of October 2013 and its consortium comprising of 14 full partners and 10 associate members covering the entire spectrum of European CH actors, ranging from academia, research institutions, industry, museums, archives and libraries. The project aims to train 20 fellows (16 ESR's and 4 ER's – 500 person months) in the area of CH digital documentation, preservation and protection in order to create them a strong academic profile and market oriented skills which will significantly contribute to their career prospects.

Digital Cultural Heritage is a complex domain that requires new requires new skills, advanced techniques and constantly upgrading know-how; for the fulfillment of which a multilevel training and an interdisciplinary collaboration among experts is necessary in order for common methodologies and best practises for the profound understanding of our past to be established. It is important to create a forum of discussion where diverse leading academic scientists, researchers, practitioners and educators are brought together to exchange and share their experience, as well as confront each others on the challenges and advancements in each of their domain. The scope of the conference is, therefore, to:

1. Encourage interdisciplinary and innovative analysis in the cultural domain
2. Promote synergies and knowledge exchange between the participants
3. Develop multidisciplinary connections for future development
4. Disseminate the results of innovative research
5. Publish the results of applied work as well as innovative concepts that would help shape our current understanding of cultural heritage

To this cause, we are seeking for original and innovative contributions in theoretical and

practical applications on Digital Cultural Heritage, in the following themes., we are seeking original and innovation contributions in theoretical and practical applications of digital cultural heritage.

[Click here to download the Call for abstract \(file/Call_for__Abstracts.pdf\)](#)

THEMES

Data Acquisition for Tangible and Intangible - Processing and Modelling

- Image matching and 3D reconstruction
 - 3D scanning & digitization (laser, structured light, motion capture, etc.)
 - Low-cost 3D reconstruction
- Heritage Building Information Modeling (HBIM)
 - 4D modelling
- Multi-source data/multi-sensors approaches

Metadata - Semantics - Ontologies

- Linked data and application
 - Authenticity & provenance
- Metadata aggregation
 - Quality metrics
- Ontology engineering
 - Principles, guidelines, and best practices
 - Application profile
- Interoperability and mapping across domains

Archiving / Use and Reuse

- Digital curation workflows & application
- Audio/video digital libraries
 - Annotations & Annotation management
 - Data visualisation
- Interactive visualisation
- Storytelling and serious game
- Mixed/augmented reality

ORGANIZER

ITN-DCH PARTNERS

ASSOCIATED PARTNERS

COLLABORATOR PROJECTS

Committee

	Nicola Carboni, Centre Nationale de la Recherche Scientifique (CNRS), France
	Margarita Papaefthymiou, FORTH, Greece
Organising Committee	Vasiliki Nikolakopoulou, Cyprus University of Technology, Cyprus
	Georgios Leventis, Cyprus University of Technology, Cyprus
	Pavlos Chatzigrigoriou, Cyprus University of Technology, Cyprus
	Matevz Domajnko, Fraunhofer IGD, Germany
Local committee	Roko Zarnic, president of SAEE, Slovenia
	Meta Kržan, Secretary General of SAEE, Slovenia
Main chair	Marinos Ioannides, Cyprus University of Technology, Cyprus

Dates

Abstract submission deadline	10 24 31 th March 2017
Notification of acceptance	30 13th March April 2017
Registration deadline	04 8 th May 2017
Conference	23 rd -25 th May 2017
Paper submission deadline	15 th September 2017

Submission instructions

Submitted contributions should be in the form of extended abstract or poster. **The conference adopts a blind reviewing process**, and the authors must ensure that any information such as affiliations, contact details, e-mails or other type of information that can help identify the authors of the papers, are removed from the submitted version.

Abstract

The extended abstract should not exceed 1000 words, including title and 3 – 5 keywords, and should focus on at least one of the scientific themes of the conference. See the template (file/abstract_template.docx) for instructions of how to format the document. Contribution not conforming with the rules outlined in the template will not be accepted.

Poster

Poster will be presented during the event by either an oral presentation or by an e-poster presentation. Please check the guidelines (file/poster_presentation.pdf)

Publishing

The ITN-DCH papers will be published by SPRINGER VERLAG in the Lecture Notes for Computer Science - LNCS (<http://www.springer.com/computer/lncs?SGWID=0-164-0-0-0>), presenting new innovative results. These papers will have a full-length oral presentation. Each submitted paper must not exceed **12 pages** in total.

Copyright form

Each contribution must be accompanied by a Springer copyright form, a so-called 'Consent to Publish' form. Modified forms are not acceptable.

Authors will be asked to transfer the copyright of the paper to the Springer. This will ensure the widest possible protection and dissemination of information under copyright laws.

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Please click here for downloading the guidelines and the copyright form (file/ITN_DCHSpringer_LNCS_Guidelines_Paper_Authors_splnproc1110_2.zip)

31th March

13th April

23rd-25th May

until 15th
September

Abstract
submission
Template
(file/abstract_template.docx)

Notification
to the
authors

Poster
presentation
Guidelines
(file/poster_presentation.pdf)

Full-paper
submission
Guidelines
(file/ITN_DCHSpringer_LNCS_Guidelines_Paper_)

Submit your Extended Abstract now

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Programme

The conference aims at encouraging the discussion between young researchers, scientists and experts in the area of digital applications for the analysis of cultural heritage object/practices, as well as exchange of ideas and opinions. One of the aims is also to inform the researchers and professionals interested in safeguarding heritage assets in earthquake prone areas about possibilities offered by digital technologies.

The conference provides the perfect platform for examining the new research opportunities and professional collaborations. Furthermore, it will support the networking between different disciplines; support the initial stage of researchers' carriers and the enhancement of young researchers' networks.

A brief outline of the goals of the conference is:

- Presentation of the final results of the FP7 Marie Skłodowska Curie ITN-DCH Project
- Presentation of the current achievements of H2020 INCEPTION Project
- Dissemination of the work done in the young researchers of different disciplines
- Bringing together the young researchers for the different disciplines supported by the ITN-DCH project and introducing them to the wider research and professional community
- Creation of a scientific space to present, discuss and divulge young investigations and enhance their scientific quality
- The exchange of ideas and opinions between different disciplines and research groups

First Workshop: Workflow for the Integration of Heritage Digital Resources

The aim of the workshop is to introduce the participants to the concept of linked data and to a selection of data curation tools that can be used for re-using and integrating data from across data silos (including examples from tangible and intangible heritage), including a demonstration of how semantically map them. The tutorial will make use of open source tools and existing standard resources for from the cultural heritage domain in order to demonstrate this process. Emphasis will be laid on the transformation of existing resources (CSV, XML etc.) into RDF, through the use of data transformation mapping tools.

The workshop will last a half day and it will promote a hands-on knowledge of several important tools that are daily used by professionals in the field. Participants will finish the workshop with a greater familiarity with both the overall workflow and strategy for creating linked data but also a basic hands-on knowledge of a number of different software and data tools that would allow them to create and manipulate their own linked data by taking advantage of existing resources in the different communities (CH, public administration, GIS, etc.). They will also have been introduced to the role of Ontologies in integrating data and how to use a mapping tool to harmonise data at the schema level to a formal ontology standard.

The workshop will make use of:

- OpenRefine (<http://openrefine.org>) together with Wikidata (<https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q5593>), Geonames (<http://www.geonames.org>), AAT (<http://www.getty.edu/research/tools/vocabularies/aat/>) and VIAF (<http://viaf.org>) for analysing, cleaning, normalise and enrich the data
- 3M (<http://139.91.183.3/3M/>) for mapping the data to CIDOC-CRM.

We are going to demonstrate the possible applications of these softwares, as well as the methodologies behind them, using diverse datasets from four museums:

- MoMa (<https://www.moma.org>) - original data available here (<https://github.com/MuseumofModernArt/collection>)
- MET (<http://www.metmuseum.org>) - original data available here (<https://github.com/metmuseum/openaccess>)
- TATE (<http://www.tate.org.uk>) - original data available here (<https://github.com/tategallery/collection>)
- CMOA (<http://cmoa.org>) - original data available here (<https://github.com/cmoa/collection>)

We specifically chose collection datasets containing information about works of art from Picasso (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Pablo_Picasso).

In order to have a unique working environment we set up a vagrant virtual machine with **OpenRefine**, some utilities and the files we will be used during the workshop. The Vagrant VM is available clicking here (https://github.com/ncarboni/ITNDCH_workshop/releases). For the instruction on how to use it please refer to the Wiki page here (https://github.com/ncarboni/ITNDCH_workshop/wiki/Virtual-Machine). Please Download it and install everything before the workshop.

In order to use 3M it is necessary to register to the service. You can do it at this address: <http://139.91.183.3/3M/SignUp?lang=en> (<http://139.91.183.3/3M/SignUp?lang=en>)

For more detailed information visit the workshop webpage digitalheritage2017.eu/workshop (workshop/index.html). The workshop material will be published on Github. You can find a preliminary version clicking here (https://github.com/ncarboni/ITNDCH_workshop).

Excursion

The third day will be dedicated to practical session and open space discussions. Three main subjects will be identified during the meeting. Two cultural heritage sites will be visited: Olimje Monastery and Podsreda Castle. On each site the use of equipment and data acquisition exercise will be presented and the discussion on various aspects of digital heritage related to visited sites will be organized.

The Workshop aims to introduce the audience in the current state of the 3D documentation in CH. Through practical session; the participants will be introduced into the most common techniques in 3D documentation of CH (photogrammetry, laser scanner, structured light scanner) and software. Additionally, the workshop has the goal to enhance the skills of the audience and create a young scientist space for debating and exchange of ideas, knowledge and trace future research and technological directions.

Agenda

ITN-DCH Final Conference on Digital Heritage Agenda - www.digitalheritage2017.eu					
TIME	23-May	TIME	24-May	TIME	25-May
8:00	Registrations	8:00	Registrations	8:30	Registrations
	Poster Exhibition		Poster Exhibition		Poster Exhibition
8:30-9:00	Opening Ceremony	8:30-9:30	Keynote Speaker: Prof. Alex Yen Asian-European Digital Cultural Heritage Network	9:00-11:00	Session V: Visualisation, VR, AR and Serious Games
		9:30-10:30	Keynote Speaker: Dr. Pavlos Chatzigrigoriou Digital Heritage for Creative and Sustainable Communities		
9:00-10:00	Keynote Speaker: Eleanor E. Fink From Virtual Databases to LOD Clouds: The Quest for Universal Access to DCH	10:30-11:00	Session II: 3D Modelling and Reconstruction in CH		
		11:00-11:30	COFFEE BREAK	11:00-11:30	COFFEE BREAK
10:00-11:00	Session I: Digital Data Acquisition in CH, Processing and Archiving of Data		Session II: 3D Modelling and Reconstruction in CH		Session V: Visualisation, VR, AR and Serious Games
11:00-11:30	COFFEE BREAK	11:30-13:00	Session II: 3D Modelling and Reconstruction in CH	11:30-13:00	Session V: Visualisation, VR, AR and Serious Games
11:30-13:00	Session I: Digital Data Acquisition in CH, Processing and Archiving of Data				
13:00-14:00	LUNCH	13:00-14:00	LUNCH	13:00-14:00	LUNCH
14:00-15:30	Workshop - Workflow for the Integration of Heritage Digital Resources	14:00-16:00	Session III: Ontologies and Metadata in Digital CH	14:00-19:30	Conference Excursion
15:30-16:00	COFFEE BREAK	16:00-16:30	COFFEE BREAK		
16:00-18:30	Workshop - Workflow for the Integration of Heritage Digital Resources	16:30-18:15	Session IV: Reuse and Assessment of Digital Cultural Heritage Data		
19:30	FREE	19:30	SOCIAL DINNER	19:30	FREE

[DOWNLOAD PDF \(FILE/TIMETABLE.PDF\)](#)

[DOWNLOAD BOOKLET \(FILE/BOOKLET.PDF\)](#)

[ITN-DCH E-BOOKLET \(FILE/ITN-DCH%20E-BOOKLET.PDF\)](#)

All speakers will be given 10 minutes to present their research work to the audience as well as additional 2-3 minutes for fruitful discussion

Session I Session II Session III Session IV Session V

Photo Gallery

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(photos taken by Matevž Domajnko)

Opening Sessions

Eleanor E.
Fink

From Virtual Databases
to LOD Clouds: The
Quest for Universal
Access to DCH

Pavlos
Chatzigrigoriou

Digital Heritage for
Creative and
Sustainable
Communities

Alex Ya-ning
Yen

Asian-European Digital
Cultural Heritage
Network

Teo Hrvoje Oršanič

Sustainable preservation of natural
and cultural heritage-seeking for
synergy
www.kozjanski-park.si (<http://kozjanski-park.si>)

Pater Ernest Benko

Sustainable preservation of natural
and cultural heritage-seeking for
synergy
www.kozjanski-park.si (<http://kozjanski-park.si>)

Venue & Transportation

HOW TO REACH THE VENUE

Clicking the link below you can book a driver that will bring you from the closest airports (Ljubljana or Zagreb) to the conference venue & hotel.

www.goopti.com (<https://www.goopti.com/en/>)

(<https://www.goopti.com/en/>)
(<https://www.goopti.com/en/>)

(<https://www.goopti.com/en/>)

CONFERENCE CENTER & VENUE

(<https://www.goopti.com/en/>)

Hotel Sotelia (Olimje, Slovenia)

(<http://www.terme-olimia.com/gb/hotels/wellness-hotel-sotelia-s-13312>)

147,25 € / night incl. tax and FULL board services

The speciality of Wellness hotel Sotelia is its close connectedness to nature. Its position, diverse structure, green roofs, and large light areas create the feeling of harmonious connectedness with the surrounding nature. We await you with special kinds of pampering that are offered by Wellness center Spa Armonia, with sophisticated catering and social areas.

Accommodation fee (special conference package) includes single occupancy of double room, breakfast, lunch and dinner and free entrance for swimming pool and fitness studio.

Hotel Breza (Olimje, Slovenia)

(<http://www.terme-olimia.com/sl/nastanitve/hotel-breza-12476>)

106,25 € / night incl. tax and FULL board services

Hotel Breza is also next to the conference venue, and it is directly connected with the hotel Sotelia and swimming pools by an underground passage.

📍 Sotelia Hotel, Zdraviliška cesta 24, 3254 Podčetrtek, Slovenia

Olimje Castle-Monastery

Olimje Castle (wikipedia)

(<http://www.terme-olimia.com/gb/hotels/wellness-hotel-sotelia-s-13312>)

Olimje Castle (Slovene: Grad Olimje) is a 16th-century castle located in the settlement of Olimje, part of the Municipality of Podčetrtek in eastern Slovenia. It is currently a Franciscan monastery.

The site of the castle is occupied since 1000 a.C. Around 1550 the complete castle was rebuilt in renaissance style and a defensive ditch to guard against Turkish incursions. In 1663 was donated to brothers of the Pauline order from Lepoglava, Croatia. Between 1665 and 1675, they completed the conversion and added a baroque church, whose altar of the Assumption of Mary is considered one of the finest baroque altars in Slovenia. In 1740, the monk Ivan Ranger painted the entire presbytery, and a side chapel was built and decorated. The Paulines also established a pharmacy, among the oldest in Europe.

The castle was nationalized after World War II. In 1974, a major earthquake badly damaged it; soon afterward it was thoroughly renovated with the assistance of national, municipal, and parish funds. The sanctuary and parish were given to the Conventual Franciscans in 1990. On the 15th of August, 1999, they revived the monastery after 217 years. Today they care for both pilgrims and the tourists visiting the historic castle and pharmacy. Due to public interest, they have also established a herbal apothecary.

HOW TO REACH

(<http://www.terme-olimia.com/gb/hotels/wellness-hotel-sotelia-s-13312>)

The transfer from/to the different airports (Zagreb, Ljubljana, Graz) can be booked at Hotel will be charged in addition upon the previous reservation.

The Podsreda Castle

The Podsreda Castle ([culture.si](http://www.culture.si))

(http://www.culture.si/en/Podsreda_Castle)

Originally known as Hörberg Castle, Podsreda was built in the first half of the 12th century by the Breže-Seliški counts (first mentioned in 1213). The high defense tower, Great Hall and tower with chapel were added to the original simple square form in a later period. The castle changed hands numerous times in the ensuing centuries, until Count Sigmund von Tattenbach acquired a permanent and hereditary title to it in 1617. In around 1848 the estate was bought by Duke Weriannd von Windischgrätz and remained in the Windischgrätz family thereafter until the end of the World War II.

There are permanent exhibitions of glassworks and an exhibition about the history of the castle. A collection of color woodcuts from around 1860 illustrating medieval furnishings and clothes, plus color lithographs of castles in Štajerska from the 1830s and 1860s donated by Kurt Müller, a regular guest of the Rogaška Slatina spa for many years. A particular attraction is a functional castle kitchen, to which the renovation has lent the appearance of a medieval kitchen. The castle is the venue for an annual Summer Music programme organized by Kozjanski Park Public Institute (http://www.culture.si/en/Kozjanski_Park_Public_Institute).

The castle has been included in the Ema's Roman Path (funded through Interreg III A Slovenia-Austria) that connects the places linked to the life of the Saint Hema (Ema Krška) in Austria and Slovenia. The Kozjanski Park Public Institute (http://www.culture.si/en/Kozjanski_Park_Public_Institute) is also a partner in the TRANSROMANICA – The Romanesque Routes of European Heritage project (funded through Interreg III B Cadses). The Podsreda Castle is one of the five Romanic monuments in Europe that form a common tourist trail. It has been cooperating also in the Interreg IVC project HIISTCAPE - Historic assets and related landscape with partners from eleven European countries.

HOW TO REACH

(<http://www.terme-olimia.com/gb/hotels/wellness-hotel-sotelia-s-13312>)

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Contact us

We are glad to answer any question or suggestion.

Talk to us (<contactus/index.html>)

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